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The effectiveness and predictive value of interventions for bridging students in Engineering Technology

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ABSTRACT

In order to stimulate a flexible lifelong learning system a student with a professional bachelor's degree can sign in to a master's programme provided that the student successfully finishes a bridging programme. Just like first-year students, bridging students experience a feeling of unpreparedness and transition problems, which results in a need for appropriate interventions. Two types of interventions can be defined: 1) focusing on orientation, positioning and preparedness before enrolment; and 2) focusing on support during enrolment. This paper included two support

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interventions: intermediate exams and individual feedback conversations. The results of the intermediate exams (i.e. mathematics and physics) are linked to students' academic achievement of February and resulted in moderate and strong correlations. Analysis did not show a straight-forward effect of the individual feedback conversations, since there are no significant differences in academic achievement between the ones who came and the ones who did not come. This does not mean that this intervention is useless since we believe that the conversations are of great advantage for the bridging students. We want to 1) encourage them to study more (if necessary) or use a different approach, 2) help them if they are facing problems during the semester, or 3) confirm that they are doing great.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning

Keywords: Bridging students, interventions, intermediate exams, feedback conversations

INTRODUCTION

There are two types of bachelor's degrees in Belgium, a professional and an academic one. An academic bachelor's degree is a precursor to a master's degree while a professional bachelor is a straight forward preparation to a professional occupation. In order to stimulate a flexible lifelong learning system a student with a professional bachelor's degree can sign in to a master's programme provided that the student successfully finishes a bridging programme (see *Figure 1*).

Figure 1. Flemish higher education system

The bridging programme focuses on the acquirement of the missing competences needed to start a master's programme and it is organized by the university offering these master's programmes. The bridging programmes at the multi campus Faculty of Engineering Technology (FET) at KU Leuven have a weight of approximately 60

ECTS, depending on the choice of study programme and the professional bachelor degree. The first semester of the bridging programme has a very general focus with mainly basic science and engineering courses (e.g. mathematics, mechanics, electricity, physics, and chemistry). During the second semester the courses are more aiming at the chosen engineering specialization of the bridging students. Just like first-year students, bridging students enter university for the first time. The FET counts approximately 800 bridging students.

1 PROBLEM

Unfortunately the success rate of the bridging programme is rather low and the dropout rates are high. These rates are comparable to that of the first-year students of FET [1]. Other studies revealed that many new students experience difficulties during the transition from secondary education to university and sometimes they drop out as a consequence [2, 3, 4]. This feeling of unpreparedness and transition problems results in a need for appropriate interventions. This previous research [1] also showed that bridging students feel significantly less well-prepared for university compared to traditional first-year students. The conclusion of this study was that there are definitely similarities between the traditional first-year students and bridging students, therefore interventions developed and organised for first-year students can be used as an inspiration source for interventions for bridging students. Two types of interventions can be defined: 1) the ones that focus on orientation, positioning and preparedness before enrolment (e.g. diagnostic testing [5] and summer courses); and 2) the ones developed for support during enrolment (e.g. Supplemental instruction [6] and assessments and feedback [7]). A time line, that starts in the last phase of the professional bachelor and ends when the bridging programme has finished, with interventions on well considered moments is developed. In this paper two support interventions are discussed: intermediate exams and individual feedback conversations.

2 INTERMEDIATE EXAMS

2.1 Context and sample

Intermediate exams are, by default, organised for the traditional first-year students at FET in the middle of the first semester, normally after five or six weeks of lectures. Thanks to these intermediate exams students get the opportunity to become adapted to the academic approach and, if necessary, they can adjust their study and learning strategies. In general, these intermediate exams account for only a small proportion of the students' final results (e.g. 10%).

The three campuses that are actively involved in this research organised an intermediate mathematics exam during the academic year 2016-2017. Only in campus x (N=99) this intermediate exam is already a real exam. If students pass this exam, they are awarded with the corresponding amount of ECTS credits. If students fail this exam, they have to do it again at the end of the academic year. In campus y (N=78) and De campus z (N=40) this intermediate exam accounts for only 10% of their final Mathematics exam result. The combination of the intermediate and final exam results in a final grade, which determines whether or not the student obtains the corresponding ECTS credits.

We also analysed a Physics intermediate test on one of the three campuses. During the academic year 2015-2016 this intermediate test was voluntary (N=37) and the result did not had an effect on students' academic achievement. In the academic year

2016-2017 (N=47) the physics test was mandatory and accounted for 10% of the total Physics exam result.

In this paper we investigate the predictive value, via regression models, of the intermediate exams and if there are differences between the different types: 1) real exam (100%) vs. limited consequences (10%) and 2) voluntary vs. mandatory.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Real exam vs. limited consequences

Table 1 shows the regression coefficients of the different models for the intermediate exams of Mathematics. When correlating the intermediate results to the academic achievement in February, strong correlations are found for the three campuses, but the strongest correlation was found for the real exam of campus x ($r=.74$). For the intermediate exams with limited consequences the correlations are somewhat lower (i.e. campus z: $r=.63$, campus y: $r=.57$).

Table 1. Regression coefficients intermediate exam Mathematics

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
Campus x	(Constant)	18.379	4.371		4.205	.000	
	Intermediate exam math	2.402	.394	.571	6.100	.000	
Campus y	(Constant)	4.982	3.782		1.317	.191	
	Intermediate exam math	3.150	.292	.736	10.778	.000	
Campus z	(Constant)	16.267	5.173		3.145	.003	
	Intermediate exam math	2.512	.499	.628	5.038	.000	

Dependent Variable: Academic achievement February

2.2.2 Voluntary vs. mandatory

Table 2 presents the regression coefficients of the two regression models for the intermediate Physics exams. For both the academic years the test results correlate significantly with academic achievement. For the voluntary test a strong correlation was found ($r=.54$), while for the mandatory test the correlation was only moderate ($r=.38$).

Table 2. Regression coefficients intermediate exam Physics

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	
AY 2015 – 2016	(Constant)	32.728	4.113		7.957	.000	
	Voluntary test	1.598	.420	.541	3.802	.001	
AY 2016 – 2017	(Constant)	13.432	9.536		1.409	.166	
	Mandatory test	1.660	.600	.381	2.765	.008	

Dependent Variable: Academic achievement February

3 INDIVIDUAL FEEDBACK CONVERSATIONS

3.1 Context and sample

Since previous research revealed that bridging students, just like first-year students, are in need of feedback [8], voluntary and individual feedback conversations were organised at one of the three campuses after the intermediate exams. The bridging students were invited via e-mail to select a moment for receiving individual feedback. An independent samples t-test was performed to find out if there are significant differences in academic achievement of February between students who came to the feedback conversations (N=33) and the ones who did not (N=14). Every conversation took about 15 minutes and students were asked the same questions. The responses on these questions were categorised and linked to the students' academic achievement. With the feedback conversations we wanted to find out if students study hard for the intermediate tests and if their results are in line with their expectations. In this research we also examined if students with bad results on the intermediate exams considered this as a wakeup call, and if so, were there some signals they would adapt their study method and/or study attitude? An answer to these questions is given by performing ANOVA analyses or independent samples t-tests. The four questions and the corresponding response categories are the following:

- “*Did you study hard for the intermediate tests?*” resulted in three response categories: 1) Yes, 2) No, and 3) Partially.
- “*Are the results in line with your expectations for Mathematics/Physics?*” resulted in three response categories: 1) Yes, 2) Better than expected, and 3) Worse than expected.
- “*Do you consider these intermediate tests as a wake-up call?*” resulted in three response categories: 1) No, because I started with studying from the beginning, 2) Yes, but I started with studying from the beginning, and 3) Yes.
- “*Are you going to use a different study approach now?*” resulted in two response categories: 1) Yes and 2) No

3.2 Results

Table 3 shows the students' mean academic achievement for the different questions of the feedback conversation.

Table 3. Results of the feedback conversations and the corresponding mean academic achievement.

Individual feedback conversations		Academic achievement February		
		Mean (%)	SD (%)	N
Present for feedback	No	33.53	22.74	14
	Yes	40.77	19.74	33
Study hard	Partially	36.41	21.33	14
	Yes	44.84	18.55	18
	No	83.93	.	1
Expected result mathematics	Better than expected	49.03	22.50	16
	Yes	35.27	19.14	13
	Worse than expected	39.43	15.35	4
Expected result	Better than expected	4.29	.	1

physics	Yes	46.38	17.53	23
	Worse than expected	26.17	16.05	7
Different study approach	No	48.14	17.93	14
	Yes	38.25	22.52	19
Wake-up call	No, started at the beginning	71.52	11.42	5
	Yes, but started at the beginning	41.12	22.13	7
	Yes	36.68	16.33	13

First of all, performing an independent samples t-test revealed no significant differences in academic achievement between the students who came for individual feedback and the ones who did not ($t= 1.099$; $p= n.s.$).

On the question “*Did you study hard?*” only one student answered *No*. This student was not included in the analysis. An independent samples t-test showed no significant differences between the students who studied hard and the ones who studied hard for one of the tests ($t= 1.195$; $p= n.s.$). Also the questions “*Are the results in line with your expectation for mathematics?*” ($F= 1.176$; $p= n.s.$) and “*Are you going to use a different study approach?*” ($t= 1.356$; $p= n.s.$) did not result in significant differences.

Since only one student stated that the result on the Physics test was better than expected, this answer was not included in the analysis. Students who stated that their results on the physics test were worse than they thought obtain a significant lower academic achievement in February than the ones that expected the achieved result ($t= 2.719$; $p= .011$).

Students who answered *No* on the question “*Do you consider these intermediate tests as a wake-up call?*” obtained a significant higher academic achievement than the students of the other response categories ($F= 7.486$; $p= .003$). These students mentioned that they started with studying from the beginning of the academic year and do not need a wake-up call. The students who answered *Yes* consider the intermediate tests as a wake-up call, but nevertheless they do not obtain a high academic achievement.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The predictive value of the real mathematics exam is the highest, which is not odd since the stakes are high. If they not pass the exam they have to do it again during resits at the end of the academic year. The intermediate exams that only accounted for 10% of the final result showed also strong correlations. So both types of intermediate exams are certainly useful. For the Physics tests, the result was not as expected, since the predictive value of the voluntary test is higher than that of the mandatory test. For the mandatory test the correlation was moderate and for the voluntary test a strong correlation was found. A reasonable explanation for this result is the following: The test of 2016-2017 does not differentiate as well as the one of the previous year, since 1) the average result of the test was much higher, 2) the results of the students were rather similar, and 3) there is a ceiling effect. To conclude, there is reason to believe that intermediate mathematics and physics exams, regardless the type, are meaningful predictors for the academic achievement of the bridging students at FET.

Analysis did not show a straight-forward effect of the individual feedback conversations, since there are no significant differences in academic achievement between the ones who came and the ones who did not come. This does not mean that this intervention is useless. Since earlier research showed that students are in need of feedback. The questions asked during the feedback conversation only revealed minor significant results. However, we believe that organising feedback conversations is of great advantage for the bridging students. During this conversation we want to 1) encourage them to study more (if necessary) or use a different approach, 2) help them if they are facing problems during the semester, or 3) confirm that they are doing great.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER WORK

By providing interventions, the ultimate goal of this research is to reduce the dropout rate and increase the success rate. To make this possible, it will be of great importance to analyse all the developed and implemented interventions. Therefore we also need to focus on the interventions that take place before enrolment and other support interventions. The interventions that take place before enrolment aim to prepare the students better for the bridging programme and/or encourage them to make a well thought-out study choice. Analysing, adapt and or develop other interventions will be the scope for future work.

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